

THE IMPACT OF STUDENTS DROPOUT OF SCHOOL IN SOKOTO STATE: A CHALLENGE TO HUMAN SECURITY

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Abstract

This paper viewed school dropout as discontinuations of educational programme by a child or students. Education is the most important instrument for national development. Every nation irrespective of its economic growth as developed, developing, and underdeveloped engineers her educational programmes towards the provision of mass literacy for the production of quality manpower for human resources and economic growth for national development. This research is a descriptive co relational type. The study was limited to school dropout within the Sokoto metropolis. A total number of 300 participants were selected through random sampling techniques. Two research questions were rose and answered. One instrument was used to collect the data, the questionnaire titled Students Drop out of School Questionnaire (SDSQ). The findings of the study revealed that students drop out of school has negative impact on human security. Therefore this paper recommended that government should encourage mass literacy.

Keywords: Students Drop Out and Human Security

Introduction

In the global perspective, it is an incontestable fact that the progress of the nations is highly dependent on the education of their citizens (Latif, Choudhari, and Hammayun, 2015). This is because education is the most important instrument for national development. Every nation irrespective

of its economic growth as developed, developing, and underdeveloped engineers her educational programmes towards the provision of mass literacy for the production of quality manpower for human resources, economic growth and national development. Thus, the nations provide financial resources for the development of human resources that will transform the economy of the

country for betterment. The realization of this made Nigeria to promulgate the Universal Basic Education (UBE) programme in 1999 to ensure that every child is enrolled in school. One of the objectives of this programme is to inculcate permanent literacy and numeracy in the Nigerian child to achieve the Millennium Development Goals.

All this is done to provide adequate literacy for the citizens and aid in promoting human and materials resources for human development and national security. However, dropping out of the school hampers human development which in turns leads to human insecurity. The paper discusses the concept of human security, school dropout, theoretical framework, and review of some related studies. It stated the method of data analysis, data presentation and analysis, and finalize with the findings of the study as well as the uniqueness of the study.

Conceptual Frameworks

This section explains the concepts of human security and students drop out.

Human Security

There are different views about Human security (Alkire, 2003). But, the most important thing about the concept is that *human being* is central. This is because he is the one to be protected. The Commission on Human Security (CHS 2003) in its final report, *Human Security Now*, defines human security as the

ability to protect the vital core of all human lives in ways that enhance human freedoms and human fulfilment. Human security means protecting fundamental human freedoms— freedoms that are the essence of life. It means protecting people from critical (severe) and pervasive (widespread) threats and situations. It means using processes that build on people’s strengths and aspirations. It entails creating “political, social, environmental, economic, military and cultural systems that together give people the building blocks of survival, livelihood and dignity” (CHS, 2003 p. 4).

The two key components of the above conception are: protection from bodily harm and means of lively hood. Protection has been defined by the CHS (2003) as the “strategies, set up by states, international agencies, Non-Governmental Organizations (NGOs) and the private sector, [to] shield people from menaces”. It refers to the norms, processes, and institutions required to protecting people from critical and pervasive threats. This protection will provide individuals with freedom from fear. Empowerment on other hand is defined by the CHS (2003 p.10) as “strategies [that] enable people to develop their resilience to difficult situations”. These two components (protection and empowerment) are interdependent. Hence CHS stated that, “both are required in nearly all situations of human insecurity, though their form and balance will vary tremendously across circumstances” (CHS, 2003 p.10).

Alkire (2003) stated that the main feature of human security is that it brings together the “human elements” of security, rights, and development. That is why it is an inter-disciplinary concept that displays the following characteristics:

- (i) people-centered
 - (ii) multi-sectoral
 - (iii) comprehensive
 - (iv) context-specific
 - (v) prevention-oriented
- (i) **People-centered:** the concept of human security considers individuals as the ‘centre of analysis’ (Alkire, 2003). Therefore, it identifies those factors that pose threats to human wants and provide solution to them.
- (ii) Human security is also based on a **multi-sectoral** understanding of insecurities (Alkire, 2003). This component of human security entails causes of insecurity relating to economic, food, health, environmental, personal, community and political security.
- (iii) **Comprehensive** approaches entails the need for cooperative and multi-sectoral responses to security threats that bind the agendas of those dealing with security, development and human rights (Alkire, 2003)..
- (iv) The **context-specific** concept of human security acknowledges that insecurities vary considerably across different settings and as such advances contextualized solutions that are responsive to the particular

situations they seek to address (Alkire, 2003).

- (v) Finally, in addressing risks and root causes of insecurities, human security is **prevention-oriented** and introduces a dual focus on protection and empowerment (Alkire, 2003).

Students Dropout of Schools

According to Latif (2015) dropping out of the school is defined by National Center for Education Statistics as leaving school without completing a high school education This definition indicated that absconding of the program of the school by the students is called school dropout. For this conception, Latif, (2015) concludes that students drop out means discontinuing schooling either for financial reasons or disappointment with their social system and examination results.

Saleh (2015) sees dropping out of high school as leaving high school without completion to a formal qualification awarded. This indicates the abandonment of an education before the expected minimum number of courses has been completed. The potential dropouts are those students that are likely to totally abandon their studies. In essence, dropping out refers to the students quitting school programs before they graduates. Latif (2015) states that students’ dropout from their schools to fulfil their financial needs. Another reason of students’ dropouts is that some parents are not interested in education for

their children. Dropout rate in Bangladesh for example is also high as in other developing countries.

This paper considers students drop out to be a phenomenon that threatens individual human security. Depending on the individuals' social maladjustment, risk factors are events or conditions that increase the likelihood of an individual's experiencing emotional or behavioral problems that may contribute to dropping out. Others include: higher mortality rate; increased social dependence; lack of, or decreased self-confidence or self-esteem; lost earnings; increased unemployment and social security benefits, and related costs;

Theoretical Framework

This paper was adapted from the "Life Chance Theory." The theory was developed by the German Sociologist, Max Weber to describe the opportunities each individual has to improve his quality of life which can only be achieved when individual are secured. It is a probabilistic theory that predicts how an individual's life will turn out. The theory has it that the available resources that an individual has, determines whether his life can improve or remains at the position socioeconomically. He lists "properties ownership, education, health care, food, clothing and shelter are the main factors that determine an individuals' life chance." Educationally, the theory implies that once an individual stay in school and acquire knowledge

there is every possibility of improving his life chances and vice versa.

Review of Empirical Studies

There are various studies conducted on the impacts of students dropping out of schools on the sustainability of the society. Latif, Choudhari, & Hammayun (2015) conducted a comparative research on the economic effects of students drop out of schools for the purpose of exploring the causes and the impacts of students drop out on the economic enterprises of the Pakistan Students. It was found that students in Pakistan like any other student elsewhere in the world drops out of school due to the following reasons: financial problems, parents' unwillingness, distance and lack of basic facilities, bad quality education, inadequate school environment and building, overloaded classrooms, improper language of teaching, carelessness of teachers, and security problems in girls' schools. The effect of drop-out was found to bedevil the economy, and human freedoms from fear and wants were created.

Yumiko, (1997) Investigated the causes, processes, and consequences of the student's dropout from junior secondary school in Komeda-Edina-Eguofa-Abrem (K.E.E.A), Ghana. The researcher carried out the research on two levels: micro and Macro. At the macro level, he surveyed 39 schools in the district. He then took up the micro investigation and surveyed 4 schools and undertook an in-depth study on them. He sampled 32 drop out

and 32 stay-in students as the subject sample of his study. He found that there were financial, gender and social cause of drop-outs of students in the Ghana. Having compared the samples, he discovered that most drop-outs engaged in apprenticeship leading to self-employment. Yet, these apprenticeship skills are gender sensitive. There are limited opportunities for women to be successful.

Statement of the Problems

Dropping out, with its many implications, remains a common term to use in describing the failure of schools and their students. Studies suggest that there is need for research in the area of student dropout to study how it affects the social, economic, and security conditions of a country.

A study on the United State of America (USA) identified that many student dropped out of their school because students found their classes boring, were absent from school for long time and unable to manage their work, spent time with those who are not interested in study, had unnecessary freedom to do everything and failed in class as the main reasons for which they left their school during their education (Agbenyega and Klibthong, 2013). The consequence of this is that the United State of America lost about \$292,000 to this threat (en.wikipedia.org). This huge amount of money affects other sectors of social development in which human

empowerment for human security is included.

In developing countries like Nigeria, dropout rates are remarkably high. Saleh (2015), states that the high school dropout problem is a crisis because it impacts not only individuals and their education, but also the economic and social costs local communities have to deal with. Communities suffer from a lack of productive workers and higher costs associated with education, health care, and other social services. She confirmed that most of the young dropouts experience a wide range of job market, earnings, social and income problems that impair their ability to transit to productive career and stable family life. Thus, their life chance is threatened.

It is disheartening that experience shows that in Sokoto State students were found to be falling apart in tertiary institutions. They are found to be dropping out of the schools. This paper therefore undertakes to assess the gravity of the tertiary students drop out in Sokoto state and examines how it affects human security in the state. The paper argued that tertiary students drop out can cause human insecurity which advertently affect state security and national development.

Research Questions

Q1. How does student's dropout in tertiary educational institutions in

Sokoto State affect the personnel security?

Q2. How does student's dropout in tertiary educational institutions in Sokoto State affect the security of people lively hood?

Objectives of the Study

This study aims to assess the extent of students dropout rate in institutions in Sokoto State and how it affects human security. The study is therefore designed to achieve the following objectives:

- i. Find out the relationship between students dropout in tertiary educational institutions and personal security in Sokoto State.
- ii. Find out the relationship between students dropout in tertiary educational institutions and security of people livelihood in Sokoto State.

Research Methodology

The research is a descriptive survey of the correlational type. The study was limited to school dropout in tertiary educational institutions within the

Sokoto metropolis. A total number of 300 participants were selected from Shehu Shagari College of Education, Sokoto (SSCOE), Sokoto State University and Sokoto State Polytechnic Sokoto, through random sampling techniques. Two research questions were rose and answered. One instrument was used to collect the data; the questionnaire titled Students Dropout and Human Security Questionnaire (SDHSQ).The instrument was validated by team of expert in Educational Management. The reliability of the instrument was obtained using test and re-test methods and a co-efficient of 0.75 was obtained. The researcher and trained field assistance personally administered the questionnaire to all respondents. The responses to the questionnaire were collected and processed with the use of Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). The statistical tool used in analyzing the data obtained is simple percentages and Person Product Moment Correlation Co-efficient (PPMCC).

Research Question 1:

How does student's dropout in tertiary educational institutions in Sokoto State affect the personnel security?

This research question was answered and presented in table 1

Table 1: Effect of Student Dropout and Personal Security

S/N Item	Students	Agree
Disagree		
1. Dropouts contribute to political attacks	85%	25%
2. Dropouts contribute to kidnapping citizens	65%	35%
3. Dropouts contribute to rape cases	70%	30%
4. Dropouts contribute to rituals killings	45%	65%
5. Dropouts contribute to armed banditry attacks	64%	36%

Item 1 in Table 1 shows that the majority of participants 85% agreed that dropout of tertiary education institutions contribute to political attacks on citizens. Item 2 shows that, the majority of the participants 65% agreed that dropout contribute to the kidnapping the citizens. Item 3 shows that the majority of the participants 70% agreed that dropout contribute to rape cases. Item 4 shows that, the majority of the participants 65% disagreed that dropout contribute to ritual killing. Item 5 shows that, the majority of

the participants 64% agreed that dropout contribute to armed banditry.

Research Question 2:

How does student’s dropout in tertiary educational institutions in Sokoto State affect the security of people livelihood?

This research question was answered and presented in table 2

S/N Item	Students	Agree	Disagree
1. Dropouts are employable for industrial security		30%	70%
2. Dropouts are interested in farming for food security		20%	80%
3. Dropouts contribute to commercial activities		55%	45%
4. Dropouts do contribute to self-employment		52%	48%
5. Dropouts do contribute as un-skills labourers		26%	74%

Item 1 in Table 2 shows that, the majority of participants 70% disagreed that dropouts of tertiary educational institutions are employable for industrial security. Item 2 shows that, the majority of the participants 80% disagreed that dropout are interested in farming for

food security. Item 3 shows that the majority of the participants 55% of the participants agreed that dropout contribute to commercial activities. Item 4 shows that, the majority of the participants (52%) agreed that dropout do contribute to self-employment. Item 5

shows that, the majority of the participants (74%) disagreed that dropout do contribute as un-skill labourers.

Summary of Findings

1. Students dropout from tertiary educational institutions contribute to personal insecurity in Sokoto State.
2. Students dropping out of schools contribute to insecurity of livelihood in Sokoto State.

Discussion of Findings

The result of this study found that there is relationship between students' dropout and personal security in Sokoto State. Therefore this affects security of livelihood and increase fear and want among the teeming population of the State. The findings from this paper agrees with Latif, Choudhary, and Hammayun, (2015) that dropping out of school by students affects the economy of the society for the simple reason that the workforce is going to be diminished. Thus human security is affected. However, the findings went contrary to the Yuniko (1997) who found that students in Ghana turn to apprenticeship and microenterprises for self-employment.

Conclusion

The paper concludes that education is a prerequisite in the empowerment of the human beings. It provides to them not only the knowledge but also the skills that will relieve them of fears of human existence and equip them to adapt to situations. The human beings can use their knowledge obtained in schools to initiate, invent, and innovate new things that can make them self-subsistent and self-employed apart from working under any organization. These empowerment opportunities provided by schools will only benefit those that were retained in schools to complete their studies. Schools can therefore be a catalyst for providing human security.

Recommendations

The paper recommends the following:

1. Government should encourage entrepreneurship program and make it compulsory for school dropout
2. The government should target schools as the centres for fighting human insecurity.

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